

EOSC - How to use it?

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Marie

EOSC – How to use it?

Andreas

Hello and welcome to today's episode of Stories of Data - the Open.Science.Talk.

Marie

Today we want to dive deeper into the magical and mystical world of the European Open Science Cloud (in short: EOSC).

Andreas

This time we get to know about practical examples of how researchers can benefit from EOSC. Like our last episode, this one is based on contributions of the EOSC Association Board of Directors and the Steering Board Representatives.

Marie

So, our EOSC-VIPs! We asked them to describe practical examples from their personal experience, in their research field or in the context of the daily work of researchers. So in today's episode we are going to present practical examples on how to support researchers in the implementation of open science.

Andreas

And what did the EOSC VIPs answer?

Marie

Well, I have again a huge pile of very interesting answers. I have them here.

Andreas

Once again, quite impressive... Take a look at this one: "Please describe with a practical example how researchers can benefit from EOSC." That was the question, here is their answer: "The primary benefit of EOSC for researchers is the ease of discovering relevant data and services. Instead of consulting multiple repositories or services, the cross-search indexes all of these so you can find what you need in one place."

Marie

A single access point is for sure speeding up the research process. And it makes you aware of content you may not have thought relevant for your work. The increased reuse of data also leads to higher citation rates and more credit for your work.

Andreas

Sounds good, so researchers are able to conduct research in a more efficient and rewarding manner. Do we have another answer?

Marie

Sure. This one points out that “The benefits of EOSC can be seen differently depending on the profile. Researchers may find in EOSC a way to structure, store, and share their data. Also, they can get properly referenced and can find, access and reuse data provided by other researchers. From another perspective, an ICT expert can find in EOSC an ecosystem of services...”

Andreas

Sorry to interrupt. What is an ICT expert?

Marie

An expert on information communications technology. And this one for example can find in EOSC an ecosystem of services to manage and implement scientific data analysis tools.

Andreas

Thanks. Learned something again. Remember, last time we learned - among many other things - that EOSC is an initiative that aims to push European academia towards a culture of open research data that is FAIR.

Marie

Yes, I remember also that you thought FAIR refers to the Fair Trade label.

Andreas

And now we know that this is another kind of FAIR. It's the acronym for findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR).

Marie

Indeed.

One of our respondents pointed out that “via EOSC you can learn how to handle your data in a FAIR way. Get to know how you can find information and train your skills in data handling. EOSC will be a place where you can search for data but also search for cooperation.”

Andreas

Zenodo, the digital repository service, is an example of a practical and easy to use tool for sharing research results that is available to every researcher. It is popular independently of EOSC but has seen a significant increase in usage linked to EOSC.

Marie

Yes, Zenodo is a nice example of a service in the context of EOSC.

Andreas

Oh, here someone wrote about the open challenges in EOSC.

Marie

I'd love to hear what they mean, especially since EOSC has already achieved a lot.

After all, digital services are already available and can be used by the researchers depending on their discipline. And in a few years, EOSC will provide a complete digital working environment for the researchers. It will offer digital tools to better collaborate and find data and scientific outputs that they can re-use for their own purpose.

Andreas

That's absolutely right. However, the point is that some of these tools are, at least today, still a work in progress. Also, one thing is still unclear: if researchers have to be aware of EOSC - or if they only have to know where to find the tools and data that they need. Like when you are using electricity, you don't always need to know the provider and how it works.

Marie

So do I understand it right, for now the digital services are depending on the disciplines and only in the future will EOSC be a complete digital working environment? Where the researchers will be able to collaborate through digital tools, finding data and research output?

Andreas

Yes, EOSC is a work in progress. To some extent, it will always be, since a data cloud will never be "done". Like the internet never will be "completed".

Marie

That is true. So let's get back to the practical examples of how researchers can benefit from EOSC. This one refers to the development of genomics: In the last decades significant progress has been achieved in the understanding of common complex diseases like cancer - or infectious diseases, such as influenza, AIDS and COVID 19. Genomics also started a revolution in vaccine development.

Andreas

Key to this major breakthrough is the large-scale analysis of databases of genomic data. This requires an appropriate analysis of large and complex datasets using mapping tools and the application of these methods to millions of phenotypes using parallelized 'Big Data' solutions. These tools are based on the Molecular Genetics Information System, called Molgenis. Uniquely, Molgenis can be used easily by clinical professionals without a bioinformatic background. It is a platform for scientific data provided by EOSC.

Marie

A large-scale analysis of databases of genomic data to make medical research easier.

Andreas

This is 'Big Data' as its best!

Marie

Another of the most visible success stories of EOSC is the collaboration to enable the COVID-19 data portal. This platform was created in 2020 in quite short time to answer to the urgent need for open data in connection to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Andreas

If our listeners want to know more about it, check: <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/>

Marie

Thanks.

Andreas

Also someone else from our EOSC VIPs wrote that “The COVID-19 emergency has strongly demonstrated the need for wider, transparent, timely and transnational data sharing among researchers facing a common challenge. In fact, the data driven transnational approach to medicine relies on a quick and effective transfer of research results to the clinical practice, where a FAIR and open approach to data could act as a real game changer.”

Marie

Though specifically in this context, I should add that FAIR data still respects privacy protection and data security – as per FAIR standards, “as open as possible, but as closed as necessary”, which is always crucial.

Here's one more very relevant example from the medical field: “Research on the COVID-19 virus, its origins, medication, vaccines but also on social consequences of the pandemic has benefited from a better exchange of research data”.

Andreas

Similarly, research on other complex societal challenges - like climate change - could benefit from EOSC.

Marie

Yes, indeed: The COVID-19 emergency is not the exception but just a further confirmation of the big scientific challenges of our time - and the ones in the future. It brings with it lessons we can now learn and put into practice in a context far wider than medicine.

Andreas

That's true. Do we have time for one last practical example of how researchers can benefit from EOSC?

Marie

Sure, and another success story can be found among EOSC-Pillar use cases: The integration of data repositories of the biomedical communities. This is a great example of EOSC: Data providers and repositories make their data FAIR and re-usable for the whole EOSC community. And the EOSC-Pillar Federated FAIR Data Space is supporting communities along the whole data life cycle, including data storage and preservation. As a direct consequence, this will increase collaboration and sustainability among the repositories.

Andreas

This is also an excellent example of the EOSC approach: Combine existing data and services, enrich them so that they can be used in a new context, and facilitate the subsequent data analysis and exploitation.

Marie

Which is also a nice bridge to our next episodes.

Andreas

Yes, right, over the course of the next episodes, we'll further discuss other toolsets designed to assist researchers across multiple fields, as well as their applications.

Marie

So next time in Stories of Data, our topic is the Research Data Management training and support catalogue - a tool that was developed within the EOSC-Pillar project. And we will welcome two very special guests - Inge and Paula from Ghent University.

Andreas

Oh really, they're coming from Belgium all the way to Vienna?

Marie

No, we will meet in the wonderful world wide web.

Andreas

Of course.

Marie

So next time people out there will have the chance to listen to four voices.

Andreas

That's great. Also this episode today was a much bigger collaboration than one might think.

Marie

Indeed. This episode today was based on contributions of the EOSC Association Board of Directors and the Steering Board Representatives, whom we want to thank at this point for their time and interest to take part in this podcast.

Andreas

And thanks also to all our listeners for their time and interest!

Marie

Yes, thank you very much. I'm really looking forward to our next podcast episode, and I hope you listeners will join us for that!

Andreas

Until then, take care, stay safe, and stay curious!

Marie

Bye!